

THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES ON ECONOMIC LITERACY OF STUDENTS IN A MODERN UNIVERSITY

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For the successful implementation of the technology of developing economic literacy, in particular financial literacy of students of higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan, regardless of their profile, it is necessary to ensure an advanced level of education in relation to pressing problems of economic activity, updating the interdisciplinary interaction of the studied disciplines with the inclusion of elements of economic knowledge.

The economics of education has a feature: it is aimed at a member of society exposed to the influence of national culture, traditions, mentality. Therefore, the tools for solving the pressing problem should be formed taking into account the national specifics and distinctive features of the student period. From a socio-psychological point of view, student life is a special stage of development, determined by the formation of independent economic activity, the desire to start independent production activities.

What is economic literacy?

Economic literacy is the ability to identify economic problems, trade-offs, costs, and benefits; analyze incentives operating in economic situations; examine the effects of changes in economic conditions and public policies; collect and organize economic data; and compare costs with benefits.

The development of literacy in the study of the fundamentals of economics involves teaching students fundamental scientific and applied knowledge in the field of economics: these are the laws of economic development, basic economic concepts, and rights in the professional sphere.

The application of digital educational technologies expands the horizons of students, opens up new opportunities for obtaining knowledge in the most structured and understandable form. Among the advantages, it is also possible to highlight minimization of paper work, simplification of teaching activities and training of students.

A financially literate person is a person who: knows how to handle monetary instruments; keeps track of income and expenses; lives within their means and plans their expenses wisely; has a “safety cushion” and leaves at least 10% of their income for investments; does not take ill-considered loans and thinks through them carefully.

In the modern world, digitalization covers all spheres of life, including education. In universities, digital technologies play a key role in improving the quality of education, providing students with new opportunities to acquire knowledge and skills. Economic literacy, as one of the most important components of student training, is also influenced by digital transformation.

Digitalization of education includes the use of technologies such as:

- Educational platforms and online courses (Coursera, EdX, Stepik), providing access to materials from leading experts.

- Interactive learning resources, such as economic process simulators and virtual laboratories.

- Financial management programs (for example, Excel or specialized financial calculators), allowing you to apply theoretical knowledge in practice.
- Mobile learning applications, such as financial games and applications for analyzing economic data. [1].

These tools not only speed up the learning process, but also make it more visual and interactive.

There are several reasons why it is important to expand the use of digital resources and apps to improve financial literacy among university students. First, digital resources and apps provide a convenient and accessible way to learn. Students can study materials at their own time and pace, using their smartphones, tablets, or computers. This removes the constraints of being tied to a specific time and place, allowing students to flexibly organize their learning and master the materials in a way that is convenient for them. Second, the use of digital resources and apps facilitates more effective learning and application of the material.

Interactive tasks, simulations, and game elements help students directly apply and practice their knowledge, which enhances their understanding and retention. Moreover, digital resources are updated regularly, providing students with relevant information and advice from financial experts. This helps students stay abreast of the latest trends and changes, which is important for developing their financial literacy and successfully adapting to rapidly changing market conditions. [2].

Modern technologies allow students to become more active participants in the educational process, and teachers to create new approaches, methods, models of learning and education. For example, the teacher can conduct an online survey at any stage of the lecture to find out the level of assimilation of the studied material.

Impact on the development of economic literacy includes:

1. Accessibility and democratization of knowledge.

Students have the opportunity to study economics from anywhere in the world using online resources. This helps to level out differences between regions and universities in the level of teaching.

2. Development of practical skills.

Modern technologies make it possible to model economic situations in real time. For example, the use of simulators helps students understand how markets work, resources are allocated, and management decisions are made.

3. Strengthening critical thinking.

Working with large amounts of data and analytical tools allows students to evaluate economic phenomena from different angles, developing analysis and forecasting skills.

4. Individualization of learning.

Thanks to adaptive technologies, learning becomes personalized. Students can independently choose topics for study and the pace of learning, which increases their motivation and engagement. [4].

Problems and challenges.

Despite the obvious advantages, the introduction of digital technologies in education faces a number of difficulties:

- Uneven access to technology. Not all students have the same level of access to modern devices and the Internet.
- Decreased live communication skills. Abuse of digital resources can lead to a decrease in the level of communication skills.

- Information overload. A large number of sources sometimes makes it difficult to choose quality materials.

Summarizing the above recommendations for improving the level of economic literacy of students, we consider it necessary to emphasize that the use of digital technologies to solve this problem is inevitable in the context of the transition to a digital economy. Given the high importance of economic and financial literacy in modern conditions, it is important to compile lists of recommended digital services in order to minimize the risks of students using incorrect or unfair information.

The set of digital services presented in this paper can be used for individual use by students to improve their level of financial literacy due to the high quality of the materials presented in them. However, we emphasize that these services cannot replace the targeted work of the higher education system to develop students' financial literacy; they act only as a supplement to it. For this reason, the integration of these services into the programs for developing students' economic and financial literacy presented by higher education institutions is of great importance.

Conclusion

Digital technologies have radically changed the process of developing students' economic literacy. They make learning more accessible, engaging, and practice-oriented. However, it is important to consider the challenges associated with their use and strive to overcome them. A comprehensive approach to integrating digital technologies into the educational process will allow students to be prepared as effectively as possible for professional activity in a dynamically changing world.

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